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THE ROLE OF THE INTERNATIONAL FUND FOR AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT (IFAD) IN ENHANCING FOOD SECURITY IN KATSINA STATE: AN ANALYTICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Food production and food security is an indispensable part of national development as any country that sufficiently develops its agricultural sector, to the extent of being self-sufficient in food, is believed to have settled one of the major challenges bedeviling it. This study is conducted to evaluate the impact of the International Fund for Agricultural Development in Katsina State towards increasing food production and ensuring food security. The study uses a multisampling technique in selecting 370 (determined by the Krejcie and Morgan formula) beneficiaries from the nine (9) selected LGAs, in addition to ten (10) officials for an interview. The study's findings indicate that the International Fund for Agricultural Development contributes immensely to increasing the level of food production by the smallholder farmers, as well as ensuring food security. It is based on this that the study recommended among others Nigerian Government at all levels should put more effort in encouraging farmers to adopt measures such as crop rotation, using organic fertilizer, application of integrated pest management through intercropping and use of bio pesticides, application of good post-harvest management practices such as proper storage, drying and processing, and application of high-quality seed stock that will further help in boosting food production and ensure subsequent food security.

Keywords: Agriculture, Food, Food Production, and Food Security.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Development in agricultural sector is continually being understood to be a crucial driver of economic transformation at global level, food security, and environmental sustainability. Food production systems across the globe are under significant pressure due to a complex interplay of challenges including climate change, rapid population growth, geopolitical instability, urbanization, and unsustainable farming practices (Yusuf & Tenon, 2019). These challenges are particularly acute in sub-Saharan Africa, where agriculture remains the main livelihood source for over 60% of the population but continues to underperform in terms of productivity and resilience. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2023) stated that the number of people affected by hunger globally rose to over 735 million in 2022, with Africa accounting for the highest burden. The continent faces a dual challenge – increasing food production to meet growing demand while mitigating the environmental impacts of agricultural expansion. Climate change has emerged as a central threat, with unpredictable rainfall patterns, droughts, floods, and rising temperatures severely impacting crop yields and livestock production. Consequently, agricultural development efforts must be both sustainable and climate-resilient (FAO, 2023).

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In spite of all this agricultural potential Nigeria has by having 72% of its 98 million hectares of land area as arable, yet, as noted by Adamu (2024), Nigeria has since the mid-70s been a net importer of various agricultural products. In a bid to address the issue, the country initiated various agricultural programmes which include the National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP), which was executed by both the Federal and Regional governments in the early 1960s to improve the production of grains such as rice, wheat, maize, cassava and cowpeas, Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) of 1975, Green Revolution Programme (GR) of 1979, National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA), River Basin Development Authority (RBDA), Agricultural Development Programmes (ADPs) that started in 1972 in the northern part of Nigeria, and the Directorate of Food, Road and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI) form part of the agricultural programmes initiated by different governments in Nigeria (Mani, 2023). Other programmes to boost agricultural production in Nigeria include Agricultural Transformation Agenda (2011), Rural Finance Institutions Building Programme (2012 – 2017), the Nigeria Incentive-Based Risk Sharing Agricultural Land (2011 to date), Value Chain Development Programme (2015 – 2019), and Agricultural Transformation Support Programme Phase I (2014 – 2019), and the Anchor Borrowers Programme (ABP) (Mani, 2023). According to Aderinto, Adeyemo and Ogunsumi (2020), in spite of the establishment of the various agricultural programmes and interventions yet, agricultural production has not significantly improved. To solve these problems, the Federal Government went into a funding agreement with the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) for the funding of small-scale farmers in Nigeria.

The International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) is a specialized agency of the United Nations, established in 1977 with the mandate to alleviate poverty and hunger in rural areas of developing countries through agricultural development. IFAD's core mission revolves around empowering poor rural men and women to achieve higher incomes and improved food security. It supports initiatives that enhance agricultural productivity, increase market access, and promote sustainable agricultural practices. In alignment with its mandate, IFAD designs and finances agricultural development projects that address the specific needs and challenges of rural communities (Kumar, Boruah, Sonia, & Padha, 2024). These projects are tailored to improve agricultural practices, provide access to essential resources such as seeds and fertilizers, offer training and capacity building, and enhance infrastructure, including irrigation systems and rural roads. By fostering inclusive and sustainable rural development, IFAD aims to create resilient agricultural communities capable of withstanding economic and environmental shocks (Holmgren, 2012). IFAD's intervention programmes in Nigeria, particularly in Katsina State, are part of its broader strategy to combat rural poverty and food insecurity (Katsina Investment Promotion Agency, 2023).

Considering the objective of the IFAD and the fact that Katsina State is a State that encompasses a total land area of 24,192 square kilometers, with 67% of this expanse, equivalent to 1.60 million hectares, for agricultural purposes (Adamu, 2024), the State is one of the best states of the federation where the Programme can best be assessed. The primary factors influencing food production in the State include the availability of suitable land and an adequate water supply, facilitating year-round cultivation of diverse crops and livestock (Katsina Investment Promotion Agency, 2023). The State also has 61 bodies of water that are suitable for irrigation – the majority of which has a combined water surface area of 558Cum situated at Jibia, Sabke and Gwaigwaye (Katsina State Investor's Handbook, 2016). This makes it suitable for the production of various categories of agricultural produce in the State that are at the same time form part of the IFAD's objectives. It is based on this that this study aimed at evaluating the success or otherwise of the International Funds for Agricultural Development (IFAD) in Katsina State from 2015 to 2024.

Objective of the Study

The study seeks to examine the overall contribution of International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) in the enhancement of agricultural sector in Katsina State and specifically to examine the contribution of IFAD in improving food production and ensuring food security among smallholder farmers in the State.

Conceptual Clarification of Food Security

According to Yusufu and Adamu (2021), the concept of food security entails the provision of sufficient food to all individuals at all times, thereby enabling them to lead active and healthy lives. This notion encompasses the availability of food to all individuals, along with the means to access it, while also emphasizing the importance of its nutritional adequacy in terms of quantity, quality, and diversity. Moreover, it underscores the significance of cultural acceptability in ensuring food security. Okolo (2016) further emphasizes that food security involves ensuring that all individuals consistently have access to an ample supply of food that is conducive to their physical well-being. This comprehensive understanding of food security necessitates the fulfillment of specific conditions pertaining to the production, demand, and utilization of food at the household level. It is crucial that individuals have access to an adequate quantity and quality of food at all times in order to ascertain their food security status. Failure to meet these conditions at the household, regional, or national levels results in food insecurity (Ibrahim & Sani, 2022). Therefore, guaranteeing the availability of food in sufficient quantity and quality is deemed a fundamental prerequisite for fostering economic development, facilitating social interactions, ensuring political stability, and safeguarding national security. Food security can be observed at various levels, including international, national, regional, state, or household levels.

However, it is worth noting that the presence of food security at one level does not necessarily guarantee its existence at another level. At the national level, food security denotes the provision of physical and economic access to adequate, safe, and nutritious food that fulfills individuals' dietary needs and preferences, thus enabling them to maintain active and healthy lifestyles. On the other hand, at the household level, food security implies the availability of food that meets the criteria of quantity, quality, safety, and cultural appropriateness, while also ensuring physical and economic accessibility to fulfill the needs of every individual. Notably, food security encompasses four key components: food availability, food accessibility, food sustainability, and food utilization.

Food security of populations is determined by accessibility and nutritional aspects. Concerning the latter, meat and its by-products and especially poultry products and eggs, have a growing importance for the satisfaction of nutritional needs, particularly those of poor households. They constitute the main source of animal protein intake and in addition an important source of revenue for the poor. Accessibility depends on prices and revenues and consequently, for a large part of the population (especially in pastoral and agro-pastoral areas of northern Niger) on the terms of trade between livestock and cereals (Karplus, 2018). An analysis of the food security situation taking into account the interactions between the two sectors - which influence the fixing of respective prices and exercise mutual multiplier effects - seems therefore essential. The absence of information on cross-border trade flows represents an important gap to be filled. The importance of the livestock sector to food security should be taken into account in the formulation of food security strategies. An initiative to improve the circulation and marketing of livestock towards Nigeria, major market for Nigerien production, constitutes an interesting option to improve food security (Macamo, 2019).

Food security remains a critical issue in many regions of the world, and Africa is no exception. The global food security challenge is fueled by various barriers to trade, such as tariffs and non-tariff barriers (NTBs). While tariffs involve the imposition of traditional customs duties on goods, NTBs include a wide range of measures that restrict the import and flow of goods across borders, through import quotas, import restrictions, excessive administrative processes, and sanitary and phytosanitary measures (Yusufu & Adamu, 2021). According to them, although tariffs, as a trade barrier, have generally received more attention as the central focus of most trade negotiations, non-tariff barriers represent a greater and hidden menace to international trade, particularly in the agricultural sector. NTBs such as import quotas, technical regulations, and sanitary and phytosanitary measures pose significant challenges to intra-African agricultural trade and hinder food security efforts.

Methodology

A survey research method is employed for the study where both qualitative and quantitative data are collected from both primary and secondary sources. Questionnaire, interview, and contents analysis are the instruments used in collecting data for the study. The population of the study constitutes 7,745 trained farmers, 1,331 farmers given improved seed, and 248 persons given climate information services – making the total target population to be 9,324. In deciding the number of samples, Krejcie and Morgan's table of sample is used. The research selects only 370 IFAD's beneficiaries across the nine (9) local government areas selected using simple random sampling technique. The distribution was made based on the number of persons in the categories and in the local governments by making use of simple percentage as described below:

Table 1: Sample Size of the Respondents

Senatorial Zone	LGA	Trained Farmers	Sample Size	Farmers Given Improved Seed	Sample Size	Persons Given Climate Information	Sample Size
Katsina South	Danja	732	29	131	05	12	01
	Kafur	814	32	210	08	13	01
	Bakori	564	22	162	06	45	01
Katsina North	Mani	784	31	122	05	36	01
	Daura	1,103	44	173	07	13	01
	Dutsi	876	35	137	06	32	01
Katsina Central	Jibia	1,045	41	157	06	23	01
	Dutsinm	958	38	101	04	61	02
	a Kurfi	869	35	138	06	13	01
Total		7,745	307	1,331	53	248	10

Source: Gambo (2023)

With regard to the persons interviewed, nine (9) IFAD's Local Government Support Officers are selected one from each of the nine (9) selected local government areas in addition to Monitoring and Evaluating Officer in Katsina State making the total number of the interviewees to be ten (10). In addition, various documents are analyzed, depending on accessibility and relevance, for the content analysis method.

Data Presentation and Discussion of Findings

The presented qualitative data was obtained from the various relevant documents as mentioned above; while the quantitative data was obtained from the 370 copies of questionnaire distributed to the selected categories of IFAD's beneficiaries across the selected local government areas. Out of the 370 copies of questionnaire administered to the respondents across the 9 selected local governments, 307 were administered to the farmers who received training from the IFAD's officials on how to improve their farming activities for more produce, 53 were distributed to those who were given new and improved seeds, and the remaining 10 copies were administered to the person who were trained regarding climate change. The researcher was able to recoup a total of 336 fully completed copies of the administered questionnaires – 281 copies from those who received training on how to improve farming and yield more farm produce, 45 copies from those who were given new and improved seeds, and the remaining 10 copies from those who were trained on how to understand climate change. This indicates that only 34 copies of the administered questionnaire, which is equivalent to 9.19% were not retrieved by the researcher. The successful retrieval of 90.81% of the total copies administered can be attributed to the proficiency and competence of the research assistants, as well as the adequate number of assistants hired. Thus, the 336 retrieved copies will be used for the presentation and analysis.

Table 2 Demographic Data of the Respondents

S/n	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	274	82
	Female	62	18
Age	18 – 25	47	14
	26 – 35	86	25
	36 – 45	146	44
	46 – 55	39	12
	56 and above	18	05
Educational Qualifications	Tertiary Education	31	09
	Secondary Education	188	56
	Primary Education	83	25
	No formal Education	34	10
Farming Experience	Less than one year	24	07
	1 50 5 years	103	31
	6 to 10 years	90	27
Daura	11 and above years	119	35

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

The data presented in Table 2 showcases that majority of the beneficiaries of the IFAD's Programme in Katsina State were males (274), accounting for 82%. Conversely, the remaining 18% of the sampled beneficiaries were identified as females making up of only 62 persons. This signifies that males are more active in farming activities in the rural areas of Katsina State in comparison to their female counterparts. Similarly, an interview with Kurfi Local Government Support Officer indicates that it is all too obvious that even though in the rural areas of the State there is no any form of occupation for both males and females which is better than farming yet, the culture of the people restricts females from taking part in many of the outdoor activities. According to him, the only females who can intermingle with males to enjoy such opportunities as the one presented by IFAD are mostly unmarried. Thus, the implication of having more males than females to the finding of this study will only be that there is no equal representation between the two categories of people in the study area, but will not have any negative impact to the finding of the study as all sort of information the researcher is in need of he can be provided with by the male majority being them the head of the family.

Table 2 demonstrates that a significant proportion of the participants to whom copies of questionnaire were administered to belonged to the age bracket of 18 to 45, representing a cumulative percentage of 83. In contrast, individuals aged 66 and older made up of 17 percent of the surveyed beneficiaries. This indicates the presence of a substantial pool of capable individuals who could actively engage in the farming activities in the study area produce more food that will subsequently translated into achieving the International Fund for Agricultural Development' objective. Therefore, having people of that age as the beneficiaries of the Programme is indications that that the programme will succeed as most of them are able-bodied.

With respect to the educational attainment of the surveyed respondents, it is evident that the majority of them have received formal education at different levels. This is illustrated by the fact that only 10% of the respondents had no formal education, while a combined total of 90% possessed educational qualification that will enable them at least be able to read and write in their mother tongue while many of them can understand English Language. This indicates that a significant portion of the respondents were equipped with the knowledge and understanding necessary to comprehend the complexities involved in the modern farming methods. Thus, this is an indication that the Programme in the study area will be of success as it deals with people with at least basic knowledge that will make it easier for them to understand whatever training given to them with ease.

Regarding the number of years the respondents have been in farming activities, it is a clear indication that the IFAD's objectives can easily be achieved in the study area as 76% of the beneficiaries as seen in the Table have more than one year farming experience and more than half of them have at least five years. This means that majority of them can easily understand the new training they were to be given as they are already in possession of some basic knowledge about farming.

IFAD's Contribution in Improving Food Production and Food Security in Katsina State

Being food central to man's progress and development, its production at a sustainable level has to be the pre-occupation of governments of all countries. It is noticeable that in Nigeria for there have been various slogans for good production, which according to Adeola and Oluwafemi (2014), include National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP), Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), Back to Land Programme, Green Revolution, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), Directorate of Food, and Family Support Programme (FSP). However, these programmes have not been successful or at least have not achieved their major aim of improving food production for the country, in spite of its vastness in terms of arable land, and still rely upon the importation of most staple food (Adeola & Oluwafemi, 2014). To boost production of food and ensure food security, especially in the rural areas of developing nations such as Nigeria, the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) was initiated as part of the United Nations (UN). The creation of IFAD was an outcome of the World Food Conference in 1974, which was in response to the food crisis during the early 70s. According to Okafor, Michael, Okoreaffia, and Nwafor (2023), IFAD contributed in no small measure in Nigeria, as it is the only specialized global development organization exclusively focused on transforming poor rural economies through eradicating poverty and hunger in the most remote areas of the world by investing in making rural economies and food systems more sustainable. According to them, IFAD targets the poorest, most remote areas where other organizations have a lesser presence because of a lack of expertise and resources.

The IFAD currently operates in various African countries, including Nigeria, and it has provided \$2 billion in funding and reached 94 countries. The fund has helped 132 million people across the globe, as of 2019 (Okafor, Michael, Okoreaffia, & Nwafor, 2023). While other programmes also invest in rural and poor areas, IFAD's projects target the poorest of the poor in the most rural areas and are characterized by small project sizes and few co-investors. This close position to smallholder farmers, communities, and other market players where IFAD operates allows for closer connections and understanding than at other programmes. For this reason, other institutions look to work with IFAD to benefit from its knowledge and resources in the field (Okafor, Michael, Okoreaffia, & Nwafor, 2023). Lele and Baldwin (2025) observed that at the time of IFAD's founding, the emphasis was on increased production by the poor for the poor. It was further agreed that IFAD would focus on the provision of financing for agricultural development projects in poor rural areas. Based on this agreement, IFAD finances loans and grants on terms deemed appropriate by the Fund, based on a country's economic status and prospects in relation to the nature and requirements of the interventions needed. In 2007, alongside other international finance institutions, IFAD introduced the Debt Sustainability Framework (DSF) that allowed IFAD to provide development finance on grant terms to countries that the International Monetary Fund (IMF)/World Bank had categorized as having unsustainable levels of debt. These terms were outlined in IFAD's Policies and Criteria for IFAD Financing, updated several times over the years, the latest update being in September 2019. It states that its major target groups, regardless of a country's stage of economic development (an important perspective, bearing in mind the graduation of several members to MIC status), were to be small and landless farmers in the poorest countries and regions of the world, such as Africa. International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) is the partner of choice for governments, institutions, and smallholder farmers in less developed nations like Nigeria, and is recognized as the premier United Nations Agency and international financial institution (IFI) that has built a clear comparative advantage in smallholder agriculture and rural development. It is recognized as a global leader in investment in smallholder agriculture, rural people, and rural communities, achieved by mobilizing and leveraging resources and by developing innovative financing mechanisms and instruments.

It continues to develop and innovate in its areas of expertise and comparative advantage, adjusting its operational priorities in response to changes in smallholder agriculture and the rural economy (IFAD, 2020). The International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) has deployed targeted development interventions, including the Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP), implemented in Nigeria since 2014 and expanded across states, including Katsina State. The programme aims to increase the incomes and food security of rural farmers engaged in rice and cassava production by promoting modern farming practices, facilitating rural infrastructure development, improving access to finance, and linking producers to markets. Beyond this, IFAD engages in a suite of integrated initiatives, including capacity development programmes to enhance agricultural productivity, economic empowerment for rural farmers, Agri-Business Capital (ABC) funds for scaling up investment, and gender-transformative (IFAD, 2022). According to Okafor, Michael, Okoreaffia and Nwafor (2023), agriculture is a source of livelihood for poor rural women and men – 90% of Nigeria’s food is grown on unirrigated plots across the country, by subsistence smallholder farmers who make up 70% of the rural population. Even though it contributed 21% of the GDP in 2015, agriculture is still undeveloped due to several barriers, which include the fact that only 46% of land that is arable is under cultivation, 95% of agricultural land is untitled, making it difficult for farmers to get financing or make improvements, poor rural roads make it more difficult to reach markets, inputs, equipment, and new technologies, which reduces farm profitability, and the availability of potable water, healthcare, and schools in rural areas is poor Okafor, Michael, Okoreaffia and Nwafor (2023) indicate that IFAD contributed immensely in improving food production and ensuring food security in Katsina in Nigeria and Katsina State being one of the selected states in the federation to benefit by the programme. Similarly, data collected from the beneficiaries in the study area, as shown in Table 3, also indicate that IFAD has contributed significantly to enhancing food production and ensuring food security in Katsina State.

Table 3: IFAD and Improved Food Security in Katsina State

Items	SA = 4 (%)	A = 3 (%)	D = 2 (%)	SD = 1 (%)
Encouraging crop rotation by smallholder farmers	183 (55)	98 (29)	21 (6)	34 (10)
Introduction of practice of conservation agriculture such as using organic fertilizer	105 (31)	162 (48)	40 (12)	29 (9)
Application of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) through intercropping and use of bio pesticides	99 (29)	204 (61)	26 (8)	7 (2)
Introduction of good post-harvest management practices such as proper storage, drying and processing	122 (36)	151 (45)	39 (12)	24 (7)
Application of high-quality seed stock	190 (57)	113 (34)	22 (6)	11 (3)

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork (2025)

The data in Table 3 indicate that the International Fund for Agricultural Development had a significantly positive impact in Katsina State as it boosted food production among farmers, especially the programme’s beneficiaries, which subsequently contributed to ensuring food security in the State. It is obvious from the data that IFAD, in its effort to improve food production in the study area, introduced a system that encouraged beneficiary farmers to adopt crop rotation. This was confirmed by a cumulative response of 84% of the sampled respondents. This shows that crop rotation, which is very important in reducing the reliance of crops on one set of nutrients, pest and weed pressure, along with the probability of developing resistant pests and weeds, was encouraged by the International Fund for Agricultural Development among the beneficiaries, which contributed immensely in increasing the amount produced. An interview with a respondent about crop rotation among IFAD beneficiaries showed that:

Crop rotation, as we all know, is a situation or practice in which a series of various types of crops are grown in the same area or farmland across a sequence of growing seasons to discourage the development of a particular pest and weed, which will be a problem to the crops ... IFAD has done a lot to convince its beneficiaries into rotating the kind of crops they grown on their farmlands so that the development of weed, pest or both that affect a particular grown crop in one farming season is discouraged by growing different crop in the subsequent year which the weed and pest cannot posed any challenged to. This practice helped the beneficiary farmers to double their produce (Monitoring and Evaluation Officer, 2025).

In the same vein, another interviewee, regarding crop rotation encouraged by the International Fund for Agricultural Development, stated that:

the common practice by many of our farmers is growing the same crop in the same place for many years in a row, which gradually depletes the soil of certain nutrients and develops the proliferation of specialized weed and pest populations. This is the major reason why farmers' produce is reducing year after year, despite the application of fertilizer. Training farmers by the IFAD officials on how to rotate crops helps them to yield more crops (Mani Local Government Support Officer, 2025).

IFAD also contributed to improving the farm produce of beneficiary farmers in Katsina State, as shown in Table 3, through the introduction of conservation agriculture practices, including the use of organic fertilizers. Data in the Table show that a cumulative response of 79% of the sampled respondents agreed that food production among IFAD's beneficiaries in Katsina state has improved due to the introduction of the practice of conservation agriculture. The result of an interview with one of the local government support officers in Daura Local Government Area showed that:

Under IFAD, food production for beneficiaries and even non-beneficiaries, as they copy from their friends [beneficiaries] in Katsina State, has increased. One of the most important practices that helped boost the production of food in the State under the Programme was the introduction of CA [conservation agriculture], which is a farming system that promotes minimum soil disturbance, diversification of plant species, and maintenance of a permanent soil cover. This heightens biodiversity and natural biological processes, contributing to increased water and nutrient use efficiency and enhanced crop production (Daura Local Government Support Officer, 2025).

Another interview conducted with the Monitoring and Evaluation Officer of IFAD-CASP Katsina State further elaborated on the conservation agriculture introduced by the IFAD to the smallholder farmers in Katsina State. The results indicate that:

...IFAD's contribution through conservation agriculture involves using reduced-till or no-till methods to avoid breaking up the soil's natural aggregates, the ecosystems within it, as well as maintaining its structural integrity. Also, under conservation agriculture, farmers were taught how to leave crop residues on the field's surface to act as a covering or by planting cover crops grown primarily to protect the soil. It also encourage diversification through planting a sequence of different crops in the same space over several seasons, which naturally breaks the life cycles of many pests and diseases and enhances soil fertility...this creates a more resilient and sustainable agricultural land space, prevents the loss of arable land, and protects natural resources that subsequently increase the produce of the beneficiary farmers.

Application of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) through intercropping and use of bio-pesticides was another mechanism employed by the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) to improve food production and ensure food security in Katsina State. Data in Table 3 show that 90% of the sampled respondents agree that food production among IFAD's beneficiaries in Katsina has increased due to the application of integrated pest management, which is a science-based approach to pest control that focuses on minimizing risks to human health and the environment while effectively managing pests that affect crops. Most of the interviewees interviewed on this regard indicated that introduction of the integrated pest management by the IFAD, which integrates both chemical and non-chemical practices, emphasizing long term prevention and sustainable management strategies increase the yield of beneficiary smallholder farmers in the study area through methods which include; implementing practices that prevent pest problems such as selecting pest-resistant plants and maintaining healthy soil; regularly inspecting areas for signs of pests and identifying them accurately for effective control; establishing acceptable levels of pest activity and treating only when necessary; as well as combining various control methods including cultural control, biological control, and physical control with the use of pesticides as the last resort.

An interview with one of the Local Government Support Officers in Dutsi Local Government Area further explained the importance of using integrated pest management as:

The integrated pest management promotes the growth of healthy crops with minimal disruption to agro-ecosystems and encourages natural pest control mechanisms ... it is a safer and more sustainable approach compared to traditional pest control mechanisms that rely heavily on chemical pesticides.

Similarly, another interview conducted with Kaita Local Government Support Officer showed the IFAD contribution in improving food production in Katsina State through the application of integrated pest management through the introduction of intercropping, which is a sustainable farming method in which two or more crops are grown simultaneously in the same field. This, according to him, improves land use, enhances soil health, controls pests, and increases production by leveraging different plant needs and interactions. He further stated that IFAD introduced bio-pesticides to its beneficiaries in Katsina State, which are pest control products from natural resources like microbes, such as fungi, bacteria, viruses, minerals, or plants, offering an eco-friendly alternative to synthetic chemicals by targeting pests with less environmental impact. Among the ones introduced to the beneficiary farmers in Katsina State by the IFAD to improve their yield are microbial pesticides, plant-derived pesticides, biochemical pesticides, and macro-organisms. Data in Table 3 reveal that the introduction of good post-harvest management practices, such as proper storage, drying, and processing, is among the most vital tools used by the International Fund for Agricultural Development in Katsina State to help improve the yield of the beneficiary smallholder farmers in the State. This assertion, as seen in the Table, received the endorsement of a cumulative 81% of the sampled respondents.

This means that the post-harvest mechanisms employed by the IFAD in the study area helped in reducing the losses of farmers from the time they harvest their crops up to the time they take them home or to markets. Many of the interviewees indicated that post-harvest management employed by IFAD involves all steps after harvesting to reduce losses as well as maintaining quality including gentle harvesting, grading/sorting, cleaning, proper packaging, curing, efficient transport, and control humidity/temperature storage that are crucial for food safety, nutritional value, and increased farmer income by preserving quality from field to consumer. An interview with Kurfi Local Government Support Officer shows that:

... IFAD's contribution in ensuring food security and more yield in Katsina State can be said to be achieved as it focused on controlling deterioration through temperature management, sanitation, humidity control, and minimizing physical damage by making use of techniques such as controlled atmosphere storage, pre-cooling, and proper handling to ensure safety and freshness which reduces the risk of damage of their farmers produce.

As seen in Table 3, the application of quality seed is one of the ways used by the IFAD in Katsina State to improve food production of the beneficiary smallholder farmers. The Table shows that a cumulative of 91% of the sampled respondents agreed that their farm produce has increased due to the introduction of new high-quality seed to them by the IFAD. An interview with one of the interviewees showed that:

Apart from the fact that the International Fund for Agricultural Development supplied and distributed high-quality seeds to the beneficiary farmers that would help in doubling their produce, it also provided them with a series of training on how to identify as well as where to buy good and quality seeds. For instance, a farmer has to consider some very vital aspects in purchasing quality seed stock such as choosing reliable sources by looking for seed companies that are certified by the National Agricultural Seeds Council (NASC) in Nigeria; exploring trusted platforms; researching top seed companies such as Premier Seed Nigeria and Value Seed; and monitoring seedling quality by selecting seedlings that are raised under uniform conditions to reduce variability and improve survival rates in harsh environments (Danja Local Government Support Officer, 2025).

The findings of the study show that IFAD contributed immensely in improving food production and ensuring food security in Katsina State, Nigeria and Katsina State being one of the selected states in the federation to benefit from the Programme. The International Fund for Agricultural Development succeeded in achieving this goal through the encouragement of crop rotation by smallholder farmers, which involves a practice of growing various types of crops in the same area or farmland across a sequence of growing seasons to discourage the development of a particular pest and weed, which would be a problem to the crops as opposed to growing the same crop in the same place for many years in a row, which gradually depletes the soil of certain nutrients and develops the proliferation of specialized weed and pest populations. IFAD also introduced a practice of conservation agriculture, such as using organic fertiliser, which is one of the most important practices that helped boost the production of food in the State under the Programme. It is a farming system that promotes minimum soil disturbance, diversification of plant species, and maintenance of a permanent soil cover. It heightens biodiversity and natural biological processes, contributing to increased water and nutrient use efficiency and enhanced crop production.

Another means adopted by the IFAD in the study area that contributed to increasing food production and ensuring food security is the application of integrated pest management through intercropping and the use of biopesticides. It is a science-based approach to pest control that focuses on minimizing risks to human health and the environment while effectively managing pests that affect crops. The introduction of the integrated pest management by the IFAD, which integrates both chemical and non-chemical practices, emphasizing long term prevention and sustainable management strategies increase the yield of beneficiary smallholder farmers in the study area through methods which include; implementing practices that prevent pest problems such as selecting pest-resistant plants and maintaining healthy soil; regularly inspecting areas for signs of pests and identifying them accurately for effective control; establishing acceptable levels of pest activity and treating only when necessary; as well as combining various control methods including cultural control, biological control, and physical control with the use of pesticides as the last resort. Similarly, IFAD introduced good post-harvest management practices such as proper storage, drying and processing in its effort to boost food production in the study area. The post-harvest management employed by IFAD involves all steps after harvesting to reduce losses as well as maintain quality, including gentle harvesting, grading/sorting, cleaning, proper packaging, curing, efficient transport, and controlling humidity/temperature storage, which are crucial for food safety, nutritional value, and increased farmer income by preserving quality from field to consumer. IFAD also achieved its goal of increasing food production in Katsina State by encouraging the farmers to apply quality seed. IFAD not only supplied and distributed high-quality seeds to the beneficiary farmers that would help in doubling their produce, but also provided them with a series of training sessions on how to identify as well as where to buy good and quality seeds.

Conclusion

The study 'International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) and Food Security' was conducted in Katsina state to evaluate the impact of IFAD in increasing food production and ensuring food security in the State. IFAD aims to increase the incomes and food security of rural farmers engaged in rice production by promoting modern farming practices, facilitating rural infrastructure development, improving access to finance, and linking producers to markets. Beyond this, IFAD engages in a suite of integrated initiatives, including capacity development programmes to enhance agricultural productivity and economic empowerment for rural farmers. Despite the fact that various studies on IFAD have been conducted in various states in Nigeria, studies on IFAD in Katsina are lacking. Therefore, this study assessed the impact of the contribution of IFAD in Katsina State. It was found that the contributions of IFAD in this regard in Katsina State were beyond measure. This study, based on its findings, made the following recommendations:

- i. i. The Nigerian Government at all levels should construct more dams and other sources of water for farmers, especially those in the extreme rural areas, to make irrigation more viable. This will help reduce the over-reliance on rain-fed farming.
- ii. ii. Nigerian Government at all levels should put more effort in encouraging farmers to adopt measures such as crop rotation, using organic fertilizer, application of integrated pest management through intercropping and use of bio pesticides, application of good post-harvest management practices such as proper storage, drying and processing, and application of high-quality seed stock that will help in boosting food production and ensure subsequent food security.
- iii. iii. The Nigerian Government at all levels should contribute towards reducing the cost of input for farmers, adoption of integrated crop-livestock-forestry systems, and creating a farm succession plan for farmers that will help in increasing their level of income, which will result in making people embrace farming activities more.

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